

1 **Direct Probe Atmospheric Pressure Photoionization /Atmospheric Pressure Chemical**
2 **Ionization High Resolution Mass Spectrometry for Fast Screening of Flame Retardants**
3 **and Plasticizers in Products and Waste**

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20 **Abstract**

21 In this study we develop fast screening methods for flame retardants and plasticizers in
22 products and waste based on direct probe (DP)-atmospheric pressure photoionization (APPI) and
23 atmospheric pressure chemical ionization (APCI) coupled to a high resolution time-of-flight
24 mass spectrometer (HR-TOF-MS). DP-APPI is reported for the first time in this study and DP-
25 APCI, that has been scarcely exploited, is optimized for comparison. DP-APPI was more
26 selective than DP-APCI and also more sensitive for the most hydrophobic compounds. No
27 sample treatment was necessary and only a minimal amount of sample (few milligrams) was
28 used for analysis that was performed within a few minutes. Both methods were applied to the
29 analysis of plastic products, electronic waste and car interiors. Polybrominated diphenylethers
30 (PBDEs), new brominated flame retardants (BFRs) and organophosphorus flame retardants
31 (PFRs) were present in most of the samples. The combination of DP with HR mass spectra and
32 data processing based on mass accuracy and isotopic patterns allowed the unambiguous
33 identification of chemicals at low levels of about 0.025 % w/w. Under untargeted screening,
34 resorcinol bis(biphenylphosphate) (PBDPP) and bisphenol A bis(biphenylphosphate) (BPA-
35 BDPP) were identified in many of the consumer products of which literature data is still very
36 limited.

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39 **KEYWORDS:** direct probe; ambient mass spectrometry; atmospheric pressure chemical
40 ionization; atmospheric pressure photoionization; flame retardants

41 **1. Introduction**

42 Sample preparation is still the bottleneck in analytical procedures for environmental, food and
43 biological analysis. Despite the numerous advances in miniaturization and on-line procedures,
44 the need of multiple steps and a large consumption of toxic organic solvents make the analysis
45 laborious, time-consuming and expensive. Ambient mass spectrometry (MS) techniques have
46 emerged during the last years as an alternative for developing rapid screening methods providing
47 high sensitivity, throughput and elucidation capacity of molecular structures.

48 Ambient MS is based on new ion sources capable of desorbing the analytes directly from the
49 sample with minimal or no sample treatment and of ionizing chemicals under ambient
50 conditions. Since the introduction of desorption electrospray ionization (DESI) at the end of
51 2004 [1] and direct analysis in real time (DART) in 2005 [2], variations of these ionization
52 techniques have been developed to broaden the field of applications or fulfilling some specific
53 analytical needs, such as easy sonic spray ionization (EASI) [3,4] and extractive electrospray
54 ionization (EESI) [5,6]. In DESI and DART, a sample surface is ionized by directing charged
55 droplets produced from a pneumatically-assisted electrospray or by a stream of excited helium
56 atoms that produce ionized atmospheric gases (such as water vapor and oxygen). In electrospray-
57 assisted laser desorption/ionization (ELDI) [7] the sample is first irradiated by laser close to the
58 ESI plume, wherein the neutrals are then ionized, thus facilitating desorption from hard surfaces.
59 DESI, DART, ELDI and analogues ambient MS techniques are highly suitable for quality
60 control processes and have been applied in drug discovery, doping control, forensic identification
61 and food safety [reviewed in 8-12], including applications for in-vivo analysis [13,14] and
62 imaging techniques [15,16].

63 On the other hand, and with the aim of extending the applicability of ambient MS to less polar
64 compounds (being this the case of PBDEs and new BFRs) desorption atmospheric pressure
65 chemical ionization (DAPCI) [17,18] and desorption atmospheric pressure photoionization
66 (DAPPI) have been reported [19]. A simpler variant of DAPCI is the so-called atmospheric
67 pressure solids analysis probe (ASAP), first reported in 2005 [20], in which the sample is placed
68 within the source vaporizer gas (usually hot nitrogen) so that the desorption/ionization takes
69 place without any additional desorption spray. ASAP has been applied to food analysis [21],
70 polymer materials [22,23] and biological [24,25] and environmental [26] samples.

71 Flame retardants are frequently applied in electronics, clothes and furniture for enhancing fire
72 safety. Due to their persistence and toxic properties [28,29] authorities have restricted the use of
73 PBDEs with a maximum concentration of 0.1 % by weight in electronic and electrical
74 equipment. Screening methods proposed in literature for flame retardants include laser-induced
75 plasma spectroscopy (LIPS) [30], total-reflection X-ray fluorescence spectroscopy (TXRF) [31]
76 and radiofrequency glow discharge (rf-GD) coupled to optical emission spectrometry (OES) [32]
77 or MS [33]. These are all based on total bromine content. The DP methods we describe constitute
78 a good alternative by offering the possibility to identify the individual flame retardants including
79 those without bromine. The direct probe is based on a similar principle as ASAP when operating
80 in APCI mode but with a different assembly configuration. The potential of direct probe (DP)-
81 HRTOF-MS with an APCI source for screening flame retardants was recently and briefly
82 discussed by our group and applied to four waste samples [34] without further optimisation or
83 validation. On the other hand, DP-HRTOF-MS with an APPI source is in this study proposed for
84 first time as analytical technique. The present study describes the optimisation, validation and
85 comparison of DP-APCI and DP-APPI methods for a wide variety of flame retardants and

86 plasticizers in plastic products and waste. DP-APPI provided a better selectivity and was also
87 more sensitive for the most apolar flame retardants, so proposed as optimal method. The use of a
88 screening software based of mass accuracy and isotopic patterns allowed the unambiguous
89 identification of contaminants at low levels required for compliance of legislation (below ~0.025
90 percentage in weight).

91 **2. Experimental section**

92 **2.1. Chemicals and reagents**

93 Information about chemicals and suppliers is provided in the Supplementary Data (SD) of this
94 article. The abbreviation system for flame retardants and plasticizers recently proposed by
95 Bergman et al. [35] were used. A number of standards of flame retardants and plasticizers were
96 used for studying the main ions formed in DP-APCI/APPI sources and making a list of target
97 ions for targeted screening analysis. The list of flame retardants studied in targeted and
98 untargeted screening is given in the Tables S-2 and S-3 of Supplementary Data (SD). These
99 compounds were new BFRs, namely tetrabromobisphenol A (TBBPA); α -, β -, and δ -
100 hexabromocyclodecane (HBCD); allyl 2,4,6-tribromophenyl ether (ATE); 2,3-dibromopropyl
101 2,4,6-tribromophenyl ether (DPTE); bis(2-ethyl-1-hexyl)tetrabromophthalate (BEHTBP);
102 decabromodiphenylethane (DBDPE); 1,2-bis(2,4,6-tribromophenoxy)ethane (BTBPE);
103 hexachlorocyclopentenyl-dibromocyclooctane (HCDBCO); 2-ethylhexyl-2,3,4,5-
104 tetrabromobenzoate (EHTBB), 2-bromoallyl 2,4,6-tribromophenyl ether (BATE) and the PFRs,
105 including tris(butyl) phosphate (TNBP); tris(isobutyl) phosphate (TiBP); tris(2-chloroisopropyl)
106 phosphate (TCIPP); tris(2-butoxyethyl) phosphate (TBOEP); 2-ethylhexyldiphenyl phosphate
107 (EHDP); 2-Ethylhexyl phosphate (TEHP) and tris(phenyl) phosphate (TPHP); tris(1,3-

108 dichloroisopropyl) phosphate (TDCiPP), tris(1,3-dichloro-2-propyl)phosphate (TDCPP),
109 tris(methylphenyl) phosphate (TMPP) and) and 3,4:5,6-dibenzo-2H-1,2-oxaphosphorin-2-oxide
110 (DOPO).

111 **2.2. Instrumentation**

112 A microTOF II mass spectrometer (Bruker Daltonics, Bremen, Germany; mass accuracy
113 <2ppm and resolution >16,500 FWHM) equipped with either APCI or APPI sources and with a
114 direct probe assembly, was employed.

115 The DP provided by Brukers Daltonics is a minor modification of a standard APCI or APPI
116 source. Differently from ASAP in which the probe is introduced laterally into the source, the
117 probe is mounted instead of a nebulizer sprayer on top of the vaporizer heater of the APCI/APPI
118 source. The nebulizer gas is directly connected to the DP and directed against it. A sketch is
119 shown in Figure 1. For the calibration of the DP-APCI and DP-APPI sources, an external
120 calibration before each run of experiments (few hours) was not enough to assure mass accuracy
121 within acceptable levels. Therefore, we introduced the calibration solution in each run by adding
122 a small droplet of calibration solution (~5 μ L) directly onto the probe after the collection of the
123 sample. DP-APCI/APPI MS parameters are given in Table 1. For confirmation purposes,
124 extraction and analysis of electronic waste and car interiors was performed by GC-APCI-
125 HRTOF-MS as described before by our research group [34] and by GC-electron capture
126 chemical ionization (ECNI)-MS or GC-electron ionization (EI)-MS for plastic consumer
127 products (see Supplementary Data). The software data analysis 4.0 from Bruker Daltonics
128 (Bremen, Germany) was used for screening by *smart formula* and *compound crawler* tools.
129 *Smart formula* provides identification on the basis of accurate mass and isotopic pattern.

130 *Compound crawler* connects with online accurate mass databases (e.g. Metlin, Chemspider) for
131 formula identification in untargeted screening.

132 **2.3. Sample analysis**

133 Samples of car interiors ($n=10$) and electronic waste (e-waste, $n=2$) from recycling plants were
134 kindly supplied by the Flemish Institute for Technological Research (VITO, Antwerp, Belgium)
135 as shredder material (less than ~ 1 mm particle size). A variety of hard plastic parts of consumer
136 products (electrical adaptors a power board, televisions and a plastic adorn, $n=9$) were also
137 analyzed as supplied. No sample preparation was required.

138 The glass probes were loaded (in the open side of the tube) with a tiny amount of sample (few
139 milligrams) by inserting them directly into the shredder material (car interiors and e-waste) or by
140 scratching the surface of the solid sample (consumer products) with the probe to release small
141 particles. The size of sample particles for DP analysis should be in the micrometer range to
142 obtain an efficient desorption/ionization. This can easily be obtained by scratching the surface of
143 the material. Main particles in the outer surface of the probe were removed with a lint-free cotton
144 cloth to prevent contamination of the source and a drop of ~ 5 μL of calibration solution was
145 added at the outer surface of the probe before introducing it into the MS source.

146 After each run (3-4 min), the probe was removed and the vaporization source temperature
147 increased to 450 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ (~ 2 min) for cleaning possible residues. Blanks (unloaded probes with
148 calibration solution) were checked between samples to prevent carry-over contamination. The
149 MS parameters for analysis are given in Table 1.

150 Data processing was done by *smart formula* tool of *data analysis* software in order to obtain
151 mSigma values (match factor between the measured isotopic pattern and the theoretical pattern
152 for a given formula) and mass accuracy values for confirmation of the analytes. Some
153 parameters, such as the number of bromine or chlorine atoms or even a complete molecular
154 formula (when studying a list of compounds for targeted screening, e.g. see Tables 1 and 2 of
155 SI), can be introduced in the tool to generate the most probable *match*. General parameters for
156 formulae generation were as follows: mass error tolerance was set at 5 ppm; H/C ratio from 0 to
157 3; number of rings and double bonds were restricted to 0.5-40. The option *automatically detect*
158 *isotopic mass* was activated. Values of < 5 ppm of mass error and <100 of mSigma were
159 considered acceptable for positive confirmation (mSigma <100 acceptable, <50 good and <25
160 excellent).

161 **3. Results and discussion**

162 **3.1. HR-TOF-MS parameters optimization**

163 Experiments were made by adding a drop (~5 μL) of a concentrated standard solution of the
164 target compounds ($0.5 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$) directly into the probe. The same major ions were observed in
165 both APCI and APPI sources. For BFRs analyzed in the negative mode, $[\text{M}-\text{Br}+\text{O}]^-$ was the
166 main ion, except for TBBPA and HBCD ($[\text{M}-\text{H}]^-$), BTBPE (fragment $\text{C}_6\text{Br}_3\text{H}_2\text{O}^-$) and HCDBCO
167 ($[\text{M}-\text{Cl}+\text{O}]^-$). For PFRs analyzed in the positive mode, the main ion observed was $[\text{M}+\text{H}]^+$,
168 except for EHDP $[\text{M}-\text{C}_8\text{H}_{17}+\text{H}_2]^+$. In the case of TBBPA, the $[\text{M}-\text{Br}+\text{O}]^-$ ion had the same
169 intensity as the $[\text{M}-\text{H}]^-$ ion in the APCI (-) and with about a 5-fold lower intensity in APPI (-).
170 Target ions with accurate mass values of the flame retardants and plasticizers included in this
171 study are given in Table 1 and 2 of the Supplementary Data.

172 The MS parameters capillary exit and skimmer 1, hexapole RF, transfer time and pulse storage
173 time also have a strong influence on the sensitivity and selectivity and can be tuned in function
174 of the m/z range of interest. A compromise was selected as optimal for the mass range of interest
175 200-1000 m/z . (see Table 1).

176 For sample analysis the instrument was operated in the highest resolution mode (*option focus*
177 *on*) and was necessary to provide a good separation between the main ions of TCIPP (327.0081)
178 and of TPHP (327.0781).

179 In general, the APPI source generated cleaner spectra than the APCI source at the same
180 temperature (more selective ionization mechanism) and, as expected, a better sensitivity for
181 highly apolar compounds, e.g. for DBDPE the signal was around 2-3 times higher in APPI than
182 APCI mode (when operating at optimal conditions in each source).

183 **3.2. APCI/APPI source parameters optimization**

184 The vaporizer temperature, APCI corona voltage and the possibility of introducing a dopant
185 solvent were studied in a sample of e-waste containing a variety of PBDEs (sample e-waste 1)
186 and TBBPA, a consumer product sample (power board) containing PBDPP and BPA-BDPP,
187 both analyzed in the negative mode, and a car interior sample (car interior 2) containing TCIPP
188 in the positive mode.

189 *3.2.1. Vaporizer temperature*

190 The source temperature is a key parameter in ambient desorption experiments, being together
191 with the corona discharge in APCI and the UV irradiation in APPI, the major contributors to the
192 ionization yield. The vaporizer temperature is a heated, insulated ceramic tube, which evaporates

193 the mobile phase or, in the case of the direct probe, desorbs the compounds directly from the
194 solid through thermal radiation. This parameter strongly influenced the sensitivity of the method
195 and was optimized.

196 In general, high temperatures are set for ASAP experiments (ramps between 100-400 °C for
197 low molecular weight compounds and 400-650 °C for polymers). The vaporizer temperature was
198 tested between 175 and 375 °C. For flame retardants in solution, temperatures around 200-225 °C
199 were high enough for ionization of every analyte in the APCI and APPI mode, while higher
200 temperatures were required to allow their desorption/ionization from solid material, especially
201 for the less volatile compounds, i.e. BDE 209 (4.0E-8 Pa vapor pressure), DBDPE (2.31E-16
202 Pa), PBDPP (5.01E-11 Pa) and BPA-BDPP (1.97E-15 Pa).

203 At the highest temperatures tested (350-375 °C), the desorption/ionization was very fast and
204 the signal-in-time too short (few seconds) for the analytes present at low concentrations. This
205 made the screening very difficult, especially in APCI mode. Furthermore, the matrix noise
206 increased with increasing temperature, thus making the spectra less clear for identification. So,
207 the minimal temperature giving maximal intensity was considered as optimal.

208 In DP-APCI, desorption-ionization of target compounds started at 175-200 °C and
209 temperatures around 250 °C gave already a maximum sensitivity for most of the compounds,
210 while for PBDPP and BPA-BDPP, the optimum was found at 275 °C. In the case of BDE 209 in
211 e-waste samples, values of 200-225 °C, although detrimental for the sensitivity, were preferred,
212 because at higher temperatures an increase in the background noise in the m/z region of interest
213 was observed (see Figure 2) that hampered the identification.

214 In the APPI source, higher temperatures were required for efficient desorption/ionization, i.e.
215 around 250 °C was optimal for PFRs and TBBPA, 300-310 °C for BFRs (including BDE 209)
216 and 325-350 °C for PBDPP and BPA-BDPP.

217 Figure 2 shows the spectra for sample e-waste 1 at different temperatures with DP-APCI(-
218)/APPI(-)-HRTOF-MS. Due to the different optimum temperatures for the different flame
219 retardants and in order to obtain a certain degree of separation between matrix components and
220 target compounds, two vaporizer temperature segments were set in the program of the analysis,
221 namely at 210 °C (0-1.5 min) and 280 °C (1.5-3 min) in APCI (-); at 250 °C (0-1.5 min) and 300
222 °C (1.5-3 min) in APCI (+); at 250 °C (0-1.5 min) and 300 °C (1.5-3 min) in APPI(-) and at 250
223 °C (0-1.5 min) and 325 °C (1.5-3 min) in APPI (+).

224 3.2.2. *APCI corona voltage*

225 Regarding the corona voltage in APCI, increasing values caused an increase in intensity and
226 these were also analyte-dependent (the lower polarity compounds being more affected). High
227 corona voltage values also caused an increase in background noise, making the identification
228 more difficult, so minimal values giving acceptable intensities for target ions were considered as
229 optimal. A value of 5000 nA was selected as optimum for the positive mode. In the negative
230 mode, values higher than 6000 nA were necessary for the desorption/ionization of nona- and
231 BDE 209, with 8000 nA as optimum to assure efficient ionization.

232 3.2.3 *APPI dopant solvent*

233 Although not provided by the instrument supplier, we introduced and optimized the use of a
234 dopant solvent into the source for increasing sensitivity (and applicability) through indirect APPI.

235 Indirect APPI is necessary for compounds without a UV chromophore and can increase the
236 sensitivity of those containing chromophore groups. Toluene, a dopant used in the literature for
237 the analysis of flame retardants with APPI [36], was introduced into the source by a syringe
238 pump (0-130 $\mu\text{L min}^{-1}$) through an additional gas port. E-waste sample 1 and car interior sample
239 2 were analyzed at 200 °C, 300 °C and 350 °C. The signal intensity of the target compounds
240 TBBPA, hepta-BDE and BDE 209 in the negative mode and TCIPP in the positive mode in e-
241 waste 1 and car interior 2 were studied. At low temperatures (200 °C) and by increasing the
242 dopant flow, the signals of all analytes increased from 0 to 100 $\mu\text{L min}^{-1}$ with a factor of 1.9,
243 2.0, 4.3 and 5.8 for TBBPA, hepta-BDE congeners, BDE 209 and TCIPP, respectively, and were
244 then constant until 133 $\mu\text{L min}^{-1}$. However, at temperatures above 300 °C there was no further
245 improvement in sensitivity by the presence of the dopant. At this point the temperature and the
246 UV radiation were sufficient for an efficient desorption/ionization. This simpler direct APPI
247 option was finally selected for the analysis of the samples, although working at lower
248 temperatures with dopant-APPI provides cleaner spectra and could be a valuable modification
249 for the commercialized DP-APPI source in the analysis of complex matrices.

250 The spectra of the consumer product sample (power board) at 200 °C, with and without dopant
251 and at 300 °C without dopant APPI (-) and at 200 °C in APCI (-) are shown in Figure S-1 (SD).
252 Similar results are obtained in indirect APPI (200 °C, with dopant), direct APPI (300 °C) and
253 APCI (200 °C) with DBDPE ca. 2-fold more sensitive in the APPI mode.

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257 3.3. Sample analysis

258 3.3.1. Targeted screening and validation of results by a secondary technique

259 Samples of electronic waste, consumer products and car interiors were analyzed with DP-
260 APCI and DP-APPI and the compounds were identified with the *smart formula* tool. Tables 2
261 and 3 show the results of the targeted screening and the quantitation and or confirmation values
262 by a standard analysis method (confirmatory technique). Values <5 ppm error and <100 mSigma
263 were considered acceptable. DP-APPI was found advantageous in terms of selectivity and
264 sensitivity. Although we could confirm the presence of the compounds with both APPI and
265 APCI, the APPI spectra were cleaner due to the higher selectivity of this source, which is
266 interesting for future applications to more complex samples. The signal of the most hydrophobic
267 compounds, BDE 209, DBDPE and BPA-BDPP were around 2-3 times higher in the APPI
268 mode.

269 Regarding the reproducibility of the method, seven aliquots of e-waste 1 and of the adaptor 2
270 samples were analyzed by DP-APPI and DP-APCI and the compounds confirmed in all of them.
271 As an example and when using DP-APPI, the main ion of TBBPA in the sample e-waste 1 was
272 confirmed with values of mass error, mSigma (isotopic pattern) and intensity (total ion current)
273 in the ranges of 0.4-5.0, 40-100 and 150000-200000, respectively. For the main ion of TPHP in
274 the sample adaptor 2, the values of mass error, mSigma and intensity were in the ranges of -1.2-
275 3.8, 0.6-10 and 200000-400000, respectively. On the basis of this results we can conclude that
276 the method was reproducible and that the content of flame retardants was homogenous enough
277 for a reproducible analysis by using only few milligrams of sample.

278 In general, when operating in the negative ionization mode, highly brominated PBDEs,
279 TBBPA and BTBPE were the most frequently detected compounds in both e-waste and plastic
280 consumer products. No BFRs were detected in car interior samples. TPHP was the most common
281 PFR in e-waste and consumer products (only not found in one TV sample), while in samples of
282 car interiors (results not included in the tables) only TCIPP was present at levels high enough for
283 detection with the direct probe ($>100 \mu\text{g g}^{-1}$). The results were later confirmed by GC-APCI(+)-
284 HR-TOF-MS analysis. TMPP was detected in one e-waste sample, one television sample and a
285 plastic adorn. TCEP was detected in one LCD television.

286 For a limited number of results we found some discrepancy between the DP analysis and the
287 confirmatory techniques. A false positive for DP analysis was for example found for BTBPE in
288 the power board and TV 1 sample. The main ion of BTBPE is less selective since it is a fragment
289 $[\text{C}_6\text{Br}_3\text{H}_2\text{O}]^-$ and various other brominated molecules can also produce it. Six different isomers
290 of tribromophenol or 2,5-cyclohexadien-1-one, 2,6-dibromo-4-(bromoimino) (CAS No 64693-
291 24-9) can cause this interference if the parent ion is $[\text{M}-\text{H}]$ and four isomers of dibromo-p-
292 benzoquinone (CAS No 1633-14-3) and 3,4-dibromo-5-ethynyl-2(5H)-furanone (CAS No
293 149418-41-7) can cause the same problem if $[\text{M}-\text{Br}+\text{O}]^-$ is the parent ion. In fact, when these
294 samples were analyzed with gas chromatographic separation prior to MS detection, we observed
295 different peaks at different retention times with this same fragment as major ion.

296 On the other hand, DBPDE, a substituent of BDE 209 was detected with DP only in the power
297 board sample and in the TV 1 sample, while by using GC-ECNI-MS it was found in all of the
298 nine plastic products. A possible interference, since the non-selective bromine fragment (m/z 79,
299 81) was used for identification with GC-ECNI-MS, or the need of further optimization of DP
300 methods for DBDPE for some matrices are possible explanations.

301 The quantitative values obtained by GC-MS were used to estimate the LOD of the method as
302 the minimal quantitative amount of target compounds measured by GC-MS that could be also
303 confirmed by direct probe analysis. LODs were based on ion signals with S/N above 10 (values
304 provided by Data Analysis program) for an averaged spectra of about 0.5 min, together with
305 acceptable mass error and mSigma screening values. A general detection limit of about 0.25%
306 w/w was estimated in this way based on the GC-MS data available. Figure S-2 shows the spectra
307 of TPHP at two concentration levels (1.6 and 14.4 times higher than the LOD).

308 *3.3.2. Untargeted screening. Identification of novel flame retardants*

309 Since, DP-APPI provided better sensitivity and selectivity than DP-APCI we applied it for the
310 untargeted screening of the samples. Two novel PFRs, PBDPP, BPA-BDPP, for which data is
311 scarce in the literature, were identified in many of the consumer products. They have been
312 recently reported in polymers [37] and dust samples [38]. In this case, the DP-APPI analysis is
313 clearly advantageous for the analysis of these heavy and low volatile molecules since any sample
314 treatment or chromatographic separation that could hamper the subsequent detection is avoided.
315 PBDPP and BPA-BDPP can be used as a substitute for BDE 209 in TV/flat screen housings and
316 other electronic consumer products [39]. They are used in a variety of polymers; PBDPP is used
317 in acrylonitrile butadiene styrene (ABS), polycarbonate (PC)/ABS, poly(p-phenylene) oxide
318 (PPO)/ high impact polystyrene (HIPS) and BPA-BDPP in HIPS, PC, PPO and PC/ABS [32].
319 This could explain the detection in many products. The identification of these new flame
320 retardants when performing untargeted screening by DP-APPI(+) is shown in Table 4. Figure 3
321 shows the whole spectra of the power board sample by DP-APPI(+) together with the spectra of
322 PBDPP and BPA-BDPP this sample. These findings highlight the need for the development of
323 wide screening tools, such as the ones proposed here, for hitherto unknown flame retardants.

324 **4. Conclusions**

325 Ambient MS techniques based on DP-APPI (and DP-APCI) coupled to HR-TOF-MS have
326 successfully been applied for the fast screening of flame retardants with detection limits of about
327 0.025 % w/w. The DP-APPI-HRTOF-MS method is reported for the first time and showed better
328 selectivity and sensitivity for highly apolar compounds than DP-APCI. A variety of PBDEs, new
329 BFRs and PFRs/plasticizers, including the novel PBDPP and BPA-BDPP by using DP-APPI,
330 have been detected in samples of electronic waste, car interiors and consumer products and
331 confirmed on the basis of mass accuracy and isotopic patterns. The results were confirmed by
332 GC-ECNI-MS or GC-APCI(-)-HR-TOF. The DP-APPI/APCI-HR-TOF-MS methods are fast
333 (few minutes), easy, inexpensive and provide with a broad scope screening for the identification
334 of flame retardants for compliance with the European WEEE directive.

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340 plastic samples.

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456 **Figure captions**

457 **Figure 1. Sketch of the direct probe.**

458 **Figure 2.** DP-APCI(-)/APPI(-) spectra of E-waste sample 1 at different source vaporization
459 temperatures. In the APCI mode at 250 °C, the spectrum of the unidentified BDE 209 in these
460 conditions is included as an insert.

461 **Figure 3.** DP-APPI(+) spectrum (A) of the power board sample at m/z 200-1200, (B) PBDPP
462 spectrum, (C) BPA-BDPP spectrum.

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Table 1. MS-HRTOF parameters

System	¹TOF parameters
Direct Probe-APCI-HRTOF	Capillary (neg./pos.) -/+1000 V End plate offset (neg.) -1000 (pos.) -500 Corona (neg.) -8000 nA (pos.) +5000 nA Dry gas 2 L/min Nebulizer 4 bar Dry Heater 220 °C Vaporizer temperature at 210 °C (0-1.5 min) and at 280 °C (1.5-3 min) in APCI (-) and at 250 °C (0-1.5 min) and at 300 °C (1.5-3 min) in APCI (+)
Direct Probe-APPI-HRTOF	Capillary (neg./pos.) -/+700 V End plate offset (neg.) -1000 (pos.) -500 Dry gas 4 L/min Nebulizer 3 bar Dry Heater 220 °C Vaporizer temperature at 250 °C (0-1.5 min) and 300 °C (1.5-3 min) in APPI(-) and at 250 °C (0-1.5 min) and 325 °C (1.5-3.0 min) in APPI (+)

473 ¹TOF detection parameters: capillary exit: ±80 V; Skimmer1: ±26.7 V; Hexapole RF: 250 V (negative mode) and
474 200 V (positive mode); transfer time: 50; pulse. storage time: 10; focus on
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Table 2. Presence of flame retardants in e-waste and consumer products analyzed by DP-APCI/APPI(-)HRTOF-MS and concentrations determined by a confirmatory technique^{a,b} in parenthesis.

	HexaBDE	HeptaBDE	OctaBDE	NonaBDE	DecaBDE	TBBPA	BTBPE
E-waste 1	+ (^a 159 µg g ⁻¹)	+ (^a 1224 µg g ⁻¹)	+ (^a 675 µg g ⁻¹)	+ (^a 886 µg g ⁻¹)	+ (^a 1855 µg g ⁻¹)	+ (^a 16232 µg g ⁻¹)	+ (^a 1689 µg g ⁻¹)
E-waste 2	- (^a 12.9 µg g ⁻¹)	- (^a 80 µg g ⁻¹)	- (^a 29 µg g ⁻¹)	- (^a 30 µg g ⁻¹)	- (^a 71 µg g ⁻¹)	+ (^a 71 µg g ⁻¹)	- (^a 41 µg g ⁻¹)
Adaptor 1	- (^a n.d.)	+ (^b 245 µg g ⁻¹)	+ (^b 150 µg g ⁻¹)	+ (n.a.)	+ (^b 8,100 µg g ⁻¹)	+ (^b 60,000 µg g ⁻¹)	+ (^b 590 µg g ⁻¹)
Adaptor 2	- (^b 30 µg g ⁻¹)	+ (^b 2,470 µg g ⁻¹)	+ (^b 1,510 µg g ⁻¹)	+ (^b n.a.)	+ (^b 18,000 µg g ⁻¹)	+ (^b 68,500 µg g ⁻¹)	+ (^b 3,700 µg g ⁻¹)
Heat sealer	- (^b n.d.)	+ (^b 1,700)	+ (^b 1,010 µg g ⁻¹)	+ (^b n.a.)	+ (^b 5,050 µg g ⁻¹)	+ (^b 70,000 µg g ⁻¹)	+ (^b 2,600 µg g ⁻¹)
Power board	- (^b n.d.)	- (^b n.d.)	- (^b n.d.)	- (^b n.a.)	+ (^b 2,700 µg g ⁻¹)	+ (^b 70,200 µg g ⁻¹)	+ (^b n.d.)
LCD TV 1	- (^b 30 µg g ⁻¹)	+ (^b 110 µg g ⁻¹)	+ (^b 110 µg g ⁻¹)	+ (^b n.a.)	+ (^b 47,700 µg g ⁻¹)	+ (^b 1,520 µg g ⁻¹)	+ (^b 190 µg g ⁻¹)
LCD TV 2	- (^b n.d.)	+ ^b 400 µg g ⁻¹	+ ^b 385 µg g ⁻¹	+ (^b n.a.)	+ (^b 88,600 µg g ⁻¹)	+ (^b 2,500 µg g ⁻¹)	+ (^b 660 µg g ⁻¹)
TV 1	- (^b n.d.)	- (^b n.d.)	- (^b n.d.)	- (^b n.a.)	- (^b 11 µg g ⁻¹)	- (^b n.d.)	+ (^b n.d.)
TV 2	- (^b n.d.)	+ (^b 2,470 µg g ⁻¹)	+ (^b 1,510 µg g ⁻¹)	+ (^b n.a.)	+ (^b 1,510 µg g ⁻¹)	+ (^b 68,500µg g ⁻¹)	+ (^b 3,700µg g ⁻¹)
Plastic ornament	- (^b n.d.)	+ (^b 260 µg g ⁻¹)	+ (^b 240 µg g ⁻¹)	+ (^b n.a.)	+ (^b 70,000 µg g ⁻¹)	+ (^b 3,700 µg g ⁻¹)	+ (^b 430 µg g ⁻¹)

Analytical techniques used for validation of results: ^aGC-APCI(-)-HRTOF; ^bGC-ECNI-MS; n.d. non detected; n.a. non analyzed

Table 3. Presence of phosphorous flame retardants and plasticizers in e-waste and consumer products analyzed by DP-APCI/APPI(+)-HRTOF-MS and concentrations determined by a confirmatory technique^{a,b} in parenthesis.

	TCEP	TCIPP	TPHP	TMPP
E-waste 1	- (^a 0.81 µg g ⁻¹)	- (^a n.d.)	+ (^a 3636 µg g ⁻¹)	+ (^a 1822 µg g ⁻¹)
E-waste 2	- (^a 1.51 µg g ⁻¹)	- (^a n.d.)	+ (^a 591 µg g ⁻¹)	- (^a 12 µg g ⁻¹)
Adaptor 1	- (^b n.d.)	- (^b n.d.)	+ (^b 140 µg g ⁻¹)	- (^b n.d.)
Adaptor 2	- (^b n.d.)	- (^b n.d.)	+ (^b 390 µg g ⁻¹)	- (^b n.d.)
Heat sealer	- (^b n.d.)	- (^b n.d.)	+ (^b 330 µg g ⁻¹)	- (^b n.d.)
Power board	- (^b n.d.)	- (^b n.d.)	+ (^b n.d.)	- (^b n.d.)
LCD TV 1	- (^b n.d.)	- (^b n.d.)	+ (^b 10,500 µg g ⁻¹)	- (^b n.d.)
LCD TV 2	+ (^b 1,230 µg g ⁻¹)	- (^b n.d.)	+ (^b 3,600 µg g ⁻¹)	- (^b n.d.)
TV 1	- (^b n.d.)	- (^b n.d.)	- (^b n.d.)	- (^b n.d.)
TV 2	- (^b n.d.)	- (^b n.d.)	+ (^b 3,600 µg g ⁻¹)	+ (^b 220 µg g ⁻¹)
Plastic ornament	- (^b n.d.)	- (^b n.d.)	+ (^b 880 µg g ⁻¹)	+ (^b 90 µg g ⁻¹)

Analytical techniques used for validation of results: ^aGC-APCI(+)-HRTOF; ^bGC-EI-MS; -non detected; n.a. non analyzed

Table 4. Identification of flame retardants and plasticizers in e-waste and consumer products after untargeted screening by DP-APPI(+)-HRTOF-MS with mass accuracy/mSigma (isotopic patterns fit) values.

	PBDPP	BPA-BDPP
E-waste 1	n.d.	n.d.
E-waste 2	n.d.	n.d.
Adaptor 1	4.0/35	-1.4/47
Adaptor 2	3.1/32	2.0/21
Heat sealer	3.8/7	1.7/14
Power board	0.7/19	-2.5/12
LCD TV 1	-0.2/56	-0.3/4
LCD TV 1	0.4/24	-0.7/15
TV 1	n.d.	n.d.
TV 2	n.d.	n.d.
Plastic ornament	1.2/17	-3.5/7

n.d.: non detected

Figure 1

Figure 2

Figure 3